

CORRUPTION IS A WEAPON OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12154551>

Abstract. In the context of the affirmation of democratic values, the commission of crimes related to bribery and abuse of official powers by civil servants discredits the authorities as a result of protest and harms the political, economic and legal system of the state. with the current government. The development of corruption in a particular country leads to the decline of that country.

Key words: Corruption, economics, citizens, bribery, social, psychology, Republic of Uzbekistan, legal, law, violent, equality, law.

Corruption is a type of crime associated with the use of official position for personal gain. Corruption activities are one of the main types of the shadow economy. In most cases, corruption refers to the receipt of bribes from the public by government officials for personal gain and enrichment, as well as the receipt of monetary income in violation of the law.[1] However, in general, not only government officials, but also citizens who do not work in a government organization can become participants in corruption relations and the provision of certain services in exchange for something other than bribery. From an etymological point of view, the term "corruption" comes from the Latin word "corruptio", which means "corruption, bribery". According to the authors of the legal encyclopedia, "corruption is a criminal activity expressed in the use of rights and powers granted to them by officials in the field of politics or public administration in order to obtain personal wealth.[2]

In fact, corruption is a social phenomenon, the roots of which lie in the shortcomings of the organization of the civil service and the specific psychology of civil servants. This indicates the need to take administrative-legal and organizational-managerial measures to combat corruption.

Corruption changes the content of managerial relations between a citizen and a state representative and has negative consequences for both society and the state. "Corruption is a social phenomenon manifested in the use of official position by public officials to obtain illegal personal gain in material or property terms.[3]

The Law "On Public Control in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted in the report of the head of our department entitled "The Concept of Deepening Democratic Reforms and the Development of Civil Society in Our Country." He emphasized that the time has come to monitor the implementation of legal documents by government bodies and civil society institutions Exercising strict public control over the activities of government and administrative bodies is one of the important conditions for building a civil society. Indeed, the activity of citizens who are not indifferent to public events, of every government employee who deeply feels that his activities are under public control, is an important condition for strengthening civil society.[8]

According to the head of our state, the more we strengthen the control functions of the state, the more state structures and bodies are involved in control, the more violence and corruption of officials will increase. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the comprehensive strengthening of public supervision and control over the activities of the state, including the activities of structures that use power. There is no alternative in this matter. In this sense, the significance of the adoption of the Law "On Public Control in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is incomparable. In general, bodies of public control of civil society, bodies of self-government of citizens turn to bodies of state power and management to make certain decisions, make inquiries on issues within the competence of bodies of state power and management, go and listen. reports of heads of government authorities and local enterprises and organizations. implementation in the fields bears fruit.

In addition, today, in order to ensure compliance with the requirements of the state order, public groups are formed and studied in the territory of the citizens' gathering, reports from the relevant local government bodies are heard and appropriate measures are taken; Measures to eliminate identified deficiencies, as well as support the activities of local government bodies, are being implemented effectively.[7] This indicates that public control is the main factor serving to establish social justice in society, balance, equality, mutual responsibility and accountability in the relations of the individual, society and the state.[4]

Today in our republic measures are being taken to establish the causes of crime, and exposed corrupt officials are severely punished. Domestic crimes are always strictly controlled by the state. In order to prevent the escalation of crime and the absence of corrupt officials, a number of long-term measures were implemented. They determine our strategy to fight crime. It has already been proven that it is wiser to use preventive measures, for example, to prevent crime rather than punish it. It is no coincidence that Article 2 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines crime prevention as one of the main objectives of criminal law.

At the moment, the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carrying out a number of activities in this direction, such as preparing draft legal documents, conducting examinations, studying the opinions of specialists and industry experts, monitoring our current legislation, consistently analyzing foreign experience.[6] The most important thing is that in order to fully ensure the implementation of the tasks set by the head of our state, propaganda and explanatory work is carried out among the general public in cooperation with state and non-state non-profit organizations.

Today, life itself shows that the goals of the fight against corruption cannot be achieved only through criminal legal means. We believe that not only government agencies, but also society, all our citizens, are responsible for combating such moral violations. Therefore, the state and society, non-governmental non-profit organizations are the most optimal way to prevent such a disease and achieve effective results in the joint fight against it.[5]

References:

1. Gulomjonovna N. D. Spiritual and Economic Factors of a Strong Family // Telematique. – 2023. – С. 7607–7611–7607–7611.
2. Нажимидинова Д. Ф. Оила тинчлиги жамият фаровонлиги // Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 12. – №. 1. – С. 77-81.

3. Каримова М. А., Нажимидинова Д. Ф. Фарзанд туғилиши ва бола тарбияси билан боғлиқ урф-одатларда зардуштийлик излари //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 12. – №. 1. – С. 69-76.
- 4.Нажимидинова Д. АЛИШЕР НАВОЙЙ АСАРЛАРИДА ИНСОН АҲЛОҚИ ВА ТАРБИЯСИ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 26-29.
5. Нажимидинова Д. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ И УСЛОВИЯХВ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ //MODERN PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. – 2024. – Т. 8. – №. 8. – С. 152-154.
- 6.Sharobiddin o'g'li S. B., Rahimberdi o'g'li X. S. Strategy of Cultural Development in New Uzbekistan //Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 11-15
- 7.Rahimberdi o'g'li X. S. BUXORO TARIXIDA MANG'ITLAR VA ASHTARXONIYLAR SULOLASINING BOSHQARUVDA TUTGAN O'RNI //AndMI Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyalari. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 96-101.
- 8.Rahimberdi o'g'li X. S., Sharobiddin o'g'li S. B. O'ZBEKISTONNING QADIMIY SHAHARLARI VA ULARDAN TOPILGAN ARXEOLOGIK YODGORLIKLAR //IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 7-8..